
AI governance around the world
Country profile: Australia

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About The Alan Turing Institute

The Alan Turing Institute is the UK's national institute for data science and artificial intelligence.

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About the project

Introduction

The international AI governance landscape continues to evolve as jurisdictions around the world balance the need to navigate increased competition with earlier commitments to advancing international alignment and cooperation on AI governance and safety. Many jurisdictions have recognised the strategic implications of AI, both for economic prosperity and national security, and accelerated investment in domestic AI infrastructure has begun to engender a more competitive international environment. However, the role of international trade and global cooperation remains crucial in realising the economic benefits of AI while effectively managing the technology's risks.

As high-level AI principles are translated into concrete policies and distinct regulatory frameworks, jurisdictions are managing the tensions between competitive and cooperative priorities. Meaningful progress towards effective international AI governance will require a clear and detailed understanding of how different countries are approaching AI governance in practice. Tracking primary source policy initiatives over the past decade, the *AI governance around the world* project sheds light on shifting national priorities on AI, dynamics of cooperation and competition, and potential areas of international alignment.

Project aims

The *AI governance around the world* project seeks to map this evolving landscape through a series of country profiles based on a consistent framework. Each profile provides a descriptive overview of a jurisdiction's approach to AI regulation and standardisation, highlighting the high-level aims and principles, definitions of relevant technologies, key policy initiatives and the main features of the respective standardisation systems. Drawing exclusively on primary sources, the country profiles analyse legal and policy instruments, national strategies, standardisation initiatives, and public investments that reflect the varied and evolving approaches that different jurisdictions are taking to AI governance.

This series offers a foundation for comparative analysis and future work on global regulatory interoperability without commenting on the efficacy of the specific governance models being adopted at the jurisdictional level. As more profiles are developed, the project aims to contribute to international understanding of where alignment is emerging and where deeper coordination may be needed.

A stylized map of Australia and Southeast Asia. Australia is highlighted in a dark orange color, while the surrounding regions are shown in white outlines against a light orange background. A small white location pin is visible on the eastern coast of Australia.

Australia

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Executive summary

Australia's response to artificial intelligence (AI) has been through voluntary tools as opposed to hard regulatory approaches. It does not have any AI-specific legislation, and AI related challenges are currently to be navigated based on existing legislation in AI-adjacent domains. Australia's most prominent policy outputs have been its AI Ethics Principles and AI Roadmap, both published in 2019. The AI Ethics Principles set out eight voluntary principles, inspired by those put forward by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) and Global Partnership on Artificial Intelligence (GPAI), while the Roadmap focuses on innovation, on the need to recruit and upskill AI workers, and on the economic benefits of AI technology.

The standards development ecosystem in Australia is relatively mature, with Standards Australia centrally coordinating SDOs. Standards are already influential in Australia's AI early policy approach, with the ethics principles referencing IEEE standards as a source of inspiration. Most recently, the Australian government published the Voluntary AI Safety Standard, which aligns with international standards, specifically ISO/IEC 42001:2023.

Key Policy Initiatives

- Nov 2019** ● **Artificial Intelligence Roadmap**
A report identifying strategies to help develop Australia's AI capability
- Nov 2019** ● **AI Ethics Principles**
Designed to ensure AI is safe, secure, and reliable
- Jun 2023** ● **Safe and responsible AI consultation**
Public consultation to assess how to mitigate AI risks
- Sep 2024** ● **Technical standard for AI use in government**
Voluntary standard for technical specialists and business owners embedding AI in government systems
- Sep 2024** ● **Mandatory guardrails in high-risk settings**
Paper proposing measures to mitigate risks from AI in high-risk settings
- Sep 2024** ● **Voluntary AI Safety Standard**
Developed as a result of Safe and responsible AI consultation
- Mar 2025** ● **AI and cyber risk model clauses**
Model clauses to simplify AI and cyber contracts

Regulatory Approach to AI

High-level aims and principles

The Australian government has stated that it wants the country to become a global AI hub by growing its domestic market through investment and training opportunities. AI is recognised as a “Critical Technology in the National Interest”, and the Australian Government has established the National AI Center (NAIC), led and hosted by the Commonwealth Scientific and Industrial Research Organisation (CSIRO), Australia’s national science agency. NAIC, in partnership with key Australian ecosystem players, such as CSIRO’s Data61 and Australian Industry Group (Ai Group), set up the Responsible AI Network (RAIN) and the Responsible AI Think Tank to uplift the practice of responsible AI across Australia’s commercial sector. It was recently also announced that Australia will establish the Australian AI Safety Institute (AISI) which will become operational in early 2026. Australian AISI will serve as a hub to support coordinated government action and giving guidance on safety and risks through established channels such as the NAIC.¹

Definitions of relevant technologies

In the absence of AI-specific legislation, there is no legal definition for AI. However, in the AI Roadmap of 2019, AI was defined as “a collection of interrelated technologies used to solve problems autonomously and perform tasks to achieve defined objectives without explicit guidance from a human being.”²

More recently, the Voluntary AI Safety Standard adopted the OECD definition and defined AI system as “a machine-based system that, for explicit or implicit objectives, infers, from the input it receives, how to generate outputs such as predictions, content, recommendations, or decisions that can influence physical or virtual environments. Different AI systems vary in their levels of autonomy and adaptiveness after deployment.”³

The Voluntary AI Safety Standard has also adopted the International Standards Organisation’s (ISO) definitions for AI, AI model, and AI Agent.⁴

Key policy initiatives

Australia has, thus far, kept to a largely soft and guidance-based approach to AI governance. Whilst there are no AI-specific regulations, there is an understanding that existing legislation applies to AI technologies, and the Australian government has also conducted various consultations over the year to decide on what best practices it should adopt to regulate AI technology. From 2019 to 2025, although the governance related developments have remained largely voluntary, there is an appetite to shift from principles and guidance to harder tools as evidenced by recent proposals for mandatory guardrails in high-risk settings.

Artificial Intelligence Roadmap

Released in 2019, The AI Roadmap was created by CSIRO's Data61 in partnership with the Department of Industry, Innovation, and Science (DISR). The aims of the AI Roadmap are structured into three core sections – 'development strategies', 'possible specialisations for Australia', and 'foundations for the future'. The report identifies three key sectors where the Australian technology sector should focus its AI developments: health, urban infrastructure, and natural resource management. These specialisations were selected based on pre-existing expertise and sectors in which Australia has the potential to offer a competitive advantage in global markets.⁵

The report especially emphasises the economic benefits of AI and its potential ability to help with the decline of Australian productivity growth since 2010, citing an estimate that digital technologies including AI may be worth up to \$315 billion to Australia by 2028.

AI Ethics Principles

Published in November 2019, and updated in October 2024, the Ethics Principles serve as a guide for both businesses and the government to design, develop, deploy and implement AI responsibly. The principles are voluntary and aim to complement, rather than substitute, existing legislation in Australia.

¹ "Australia Establishes New Institute to Strengthen AI Safety." Australian Government. November 25, 2025. <https://www.industry.gov.au/news/australia-establishes-new-institute-strengthen-ai-safety>.

² "Artificial Intelligence Roadmap." CSIRO. November, 2019. <https://www.csiro.au/en/research/technology-space/ai/artificial-intelligence-roadmap>.

³ "Terms and Definitions | Voluntary AI Safety Standard." CSIRO. 2024. <https://www.csiro.au/https://www.industry.gov.au/publications/voluntary-ai-safety-standard/terms-and-definitions>.

⁴ Ibid.

⁵ 'Artificial Intelligence Roadmap - CSIRO'. <https://www.csiro.au/en/research/technology-space/ai/artificial-intelligence-roadmap>

Australia put forth eight principles, namely: Human, societal and environmental wellbeing; Human-centred values; Fairness; Privacy protection and security; Reliability and safety; Transparency and explainability; Contestability; and Accountability.⁶

Threshold questions for applying AI Ethics Principles

To facilitate application of the principles, the government has also included two threshold questions for organisation's to consider:

- Will the AI system you are developing or implementing be used to make decisions or in other ways have a significant impact (positive or negative) on people (including marginalised groups), the environment or society?
- Are you unsure about how the AI system may impact your organisation or your customers/clients?

Since 2019, the government has been focusing on operationalizing AI technology. NAIC has released Implementing Australia's AI Ethics Principles Report⁷ to provide practical guidance and practices to Australian businesses to implement the eight ethics principles and CSIRO's Data61 has released several best practices to support responsible AI practices, such as the CSIRO Responsible AI Pattern Catalogue and the Responsible AI ESG Framework for investors.

Safe and responsible AI in Australia consultation and response

On 1 June 2023, The Australian government opened a public consultation to the needed steps to mitigate AI risks and the fit of different governance mechanisms including standards, regulation, frameworks, and principles.⁸ The consultation received 510 online submissions from a variety of stakeholders from industry, academia, civil society, the public, and legal entities. On 17 January 2024, the government published its response citing concerns about harms and the potential need for regulatory mechanisms to address these in high risk instances without making regulatory barriers too high for low risk systems.⁹

⁶ "Australia's AI Ethics Principles." Australian Government | Department of Industry, Science and Resources. November, 2019. <https://www.industry.gov.au/publications/australias-artificial-intelligence-ethics-principles/australias-ai-ethics-principles>.

⁷ Reid, Alistair, Simon O'Callaghan, and Yaya Lu. "Implementing Australia's AI Ethics Principles: A Selection of Responsible AI Practices and Resources." CSIRO's NAIC, 2023.

⁸ "Safe and Responsible AI in Australia Discussion Paper." Australian Government | Department of Industry, Science and Resources, June 1, 2023. https://storage.googleapis.com/converlens-au-industry/industry/p/prj2452c8e24d7a400c72429/public_assets/Safe-and-responsible-AI-in-Australia.pdf.

⁹ "Safe and Responsible AI in Australia Consultation: Australian Government's Interim Response." Australian Government | Department of Industry, Science and Resources, January 17, 2024. https://storage.googleapis.com/converlens-au-industry/industry/p/prj2452c8e24d7a400c72429/public_assets/safe-and-responsible-ai-in-australia-governments-interim-response.pdf.

Australian Human Rights Commission: Human Rights and technology report.

In 2021, the Australian Human Rights Commission published a report on the human rights implications of technologies, with a particular focus on AI regulation.

AI transparency is discussed at length, with the report recommending that individuals be informed when a decision concerning them was made using AI. The commission likewise advocates for “legislation prohibit(ing) the use of ‘black box’ or opaque AI in decision making by non-government entities”, as well as for government support to aid organisations in providing better explanations of AI decisions. The report also pushes for recourse mechanisms, so that “individuals (are) given a practical means of appealing to a body that can review AI-informed decisions by non-government entities”.¹⁰

A later section of the report surveys current and upcoming governance mechanisms. The commission recommends the adoption and implementation of standards and certification schemes, human rights impact assessments, regulatory sandboxes, and the establishment of an independent AI Safety Commissioner.¹¹

Proposal paper: introducing mandatory guardrails for AI in high-risk settings

Response from the Safe and responsible AI consultation had revealed that Australia’s currently regulatory framework was not fit to respond to AI risks. As a result, the government put forth a proposal paper to get views on:

- Guardrails proposed in the paper
- Proposed definition for high-risk AI
- Regulatory options for mandating guardrails¹²

The proposed guardrails, if implemented, will serve a preventative role. The guardrails are also grounded in measures such as testing, transparency, and accountability.¹³

Australia’s proposed mandatory guardrails for AI in high risk settings¹⁴

Organisations developing or deploying high-risk AI systems are required to:

¹⁰ “Artificial Intelligence in Public Services.” Equality and Human Rights Commission. 2022.

https://www.equalityhumanrights.com/en/advice-and-guidance/artificial-intelligence-public-services?utm_source=LinkedIn&utm_medium=social&utm_campaign=Orlo.

¹¹ Equality and Human Rights Commission, 109.

¹² “Implementing Australia’s AI Ethics Principles: A Selection of Responsible AI Practices and Resources.” Introducing Mandatory Guardrails for AI in High-risk Settings: Proposals Paper. Australian Government | Department of Industry, Science and Resources, September 5, 2024. <https://consult.industry.gov.au/ai-mandatory-guardrails>.

¹³ “Safe and Responsible AI in Australia Proposals Paper for Introducing Mandatory Guardrails for AI in High-risk Settings.” Australian Government | Department of Industry, Science and Resources, September 5, 2024.

https://storage.googleapis.com/converlens-au-industry/industry/p/prj2452c8e24d7a400c72429/public_assets/safe-and-responsible-ai-in-australia-governments-interim-response.pdf.

¹⁴ Ibid.

1. Establish, implement and publish an accountability process including governance, internal capability and a strategy for regulatory compliance
2. Establish and implement a risk management process to identify and mitigate risks
3. Protect AI systems, and implement data governance measures to manage data quality and provenance
4. Test AI models and systems to evaluate model performance and monitor the system once deployed
5. Enable human control or intervention in an AI system to achieve meaningful human oversight
6. Inform end-users regarding AI-enabled decisions, interactions with AI and AI-generated content
7. Establish processes for people impacted by AI systems to challenge use or outcomes
8. Be transparent with other organisations across the AI supply chain about data, models and systems to help them effectively address risks
9. Keep and maintain records to allow third parties to assess compliance with guardrails
10. Undertake conformity assessments to demonstrate and certify compliance with the guardrails

To the extent of defining high-risk AI, the government proposed a principles-based approach to designating an AI system as high-risk, as opposed to the list based approach under the EU AI Act. The rationale offered for this approach is that it offers flexibility in scenarios where inadvertently low-risk applications can be caught in a list of high-risk setting.¹⁵ The proposed principles state that in designating a system as high-risk, in light of the severity and extent of adverse impact, regard must be given to:¹⁶

- individual's rights recognised in Australia's human rights law
- individuals' mental health or safety
- legal effects, defamation or similarly significant effects on an individual
- groups of individuals or collective rights of cultural groups
- the broader Australian economy, society, environment and rule of law

Finally, the paper also proposes three regulatory options:¹⁷

1. A domain specific approach that integrates guardrails into existing regulatory frameworks
2. A framework approach that introduces new legislation to adapt existing regulatory frameworks across the economy
3. A whole of economy approach which introduces an AI-specific legislation

¹⁵ Ibid.

¹⁶ Ibid.

¹⁷ Ibid.

AI and cyber risk model clauses

To simplify contracts pertaining to information and communication technologies, the Australian government has created a collection of AI and cyber risk model clauses that can be used for contracts involving existing AI systems, products with embedded AI, or internal AI tool development.¹⁸

New South Wales AI Assurance Framework

Effective March 2022, the government of New South Wales put forward an AI Assurance Framework. Mandatory for all government projects containing an AI component – with an exception for projects that utilise a large commercial AI application without significant modification – the framework requires the submission of an impact self-assessment to an internal NSW AI review committee.¹⁹

¹⁸ "AI and Cyber Risk Model Clauses." Australian Government | BuyICT, https://www.buyict.gov.au/sp?id=kb_article_view&sys_id=930835cf9754ea9025abff4ef053aff9&entry=front_page.

¹⁹ "NSW Artificial Intelligence Assurance Framework | Digital.NSW". <https://www.digital.nsw.gov.au/policy/artificial-intelligence/nsw-artificial-intelligence-assurance-framework>.

Approach to AI Standardisation

Main features of the standardisation system

Standards Australia (SA) is the country's national standards body. An independent non-profit organisation, SA represents Australia at ISO and IEC. SA both develops standards through its own technical committees and accredits other organisations to develop Australian standards. By default, standards in Australia are voluntary; however, compliance can be made mandatory if a standard is directly referred to in Australian or joint Australian and New Zealand law.

National AI-focused standardisation activities

Domestic AI standardisation work is relatively developed. SA has a dedicated subcommittee for AI which contributes to and adopts standards from ISO/IEC for domestic use.

In 2020, SA published its AI Standards Roadmap. The roadmap provides recommendations for increasing Australia's – and in particular, IT-043, Australia's SC 42 mirror committee's – influence in international AI standardisation. The document examines expertise gaps in IT-043's membership, noting financial services, agriculture, and elder care as problem areas.

SA also recommended a direct text adoption of ISO/IEC 27701, a privacy management standard, into law to improve interoperability between Australia and GDPR countries, and the formation of an Australian AI Standards Hub to improve collaboration between SDOs and Industry.²⁰

Aside from SA, the NAIC has also been active in publishing standards, most prominently the Voluntary AI Safety Standard, which was developed following the interim response to the Safe and responsible AI consultation.²¹ This standard sits alongside other 5 pillars that were identified as action points in the interim response, namely, Proposals Paper for Introducing Mandatory Guardrails for AI in High-Risk Settings, the National Framework for the Assurance of Artificial Intelligence in

²⁰ Standards Australia, 'An Artificial Intelligence Standards Roadmap: Making Australia's Voice Heard', 2020, <https://www.standards.org.au/news/standards-australia-sets-priorities-for-artificial-intelligence>.

²¹ "Voluntary AI Safety Standard | Guiding Safe and Responsible Use of Artificial Intelligence in Australia." Australian Government | Department of Industry, Science and Resources, September 5, 2024. <https://www.industry.gov.au/publications/voluntary-ai-safety-standard>.

Government and the Policy for Responsible Use of AI in Government.²² The Voluntary AI Safety Standard includes 10 guardrails, and is designed to guide organisations to implement AI safely and responsibly, protect people and communities from harm, guard against reputational and financial risks, and build user and organisational trust in AI systems, among other things.

Moreover, the Digital Transformation Agency has also developed an AI technical standard for the Australian government.²³ It provides practical guidance for technical specialists and business owners to embed AI in government systems. It sets an agency-first approach which focuses on reusing existing agency policies rather than creating new ones.²⁴ The standard's target audience is broad and along with the government, it also includes civil society, oversight bodies, industry partners, and various other external stakeholders.²⁵ It adopts a whole of government approach and also identifies accountable officials, requires staff training, and is accompanied with a requirement that agencies share a publicly available statement which outlines their policy on AI adoption.²⁶

Engagement in international AI standardisation

Australia is active in international AI standardisation forums. SA is a participating member of ISO/IEC JTC 1/SC 42. The SDO has directly adopted SC42 standards, including ISO/IEC TR24027:2021 – Bias in AI systems and AI aided decision-making.²⁷

²² "Why We Wrote the Standard." Australian Government | Department of Industry, Science and Resources. <https://www.industry.gov.au/publications/voluntary-ai-safety-standard/why-we-wrote-standard>.

²³ "Technical Standard for Government's Use of Artificial Intelligence." Australian Government. <https://www.digital.gov.au/policy/ai/AI-technical-standard>.

²⁴ "Technical Standard for Government's Use of Artificial Intelligence: Introduction, Scope and Target Audience." Australian Government. <https://www.digital.gov.au/policy/ai/AI-technical-standard/technical-standard-governments-use-artificial-intelligence-introduction-scope-and-target-audience>.

²⁵ Ibid.

²⁶ Ibid.

²⁷ 'SA TR ISO/IEC 24027:2022 | Standards Australia'. <https://store.standards.org.au/product/sa-tr-iso-iec-24027-2022>.

